

CODING FRAMEWORK FOR BFW

THEME	SUBTHEME	CODES
medication taken	Types of drugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARVS • coartem
Experiences of breastfeeding	Experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • medication is strong, you need to take plenty of fluids and eat since the baby needs to breastfeed. • the child who is exclusively breastfed for 6 months is healthy and the breastmilk boots the immunity of the baby. • A breastfeeding woman needs to be careful to avoid any illness because I think the baby may contract the illness when breastfeeding • I have used herbal: Kamunye after delivery for healing of the lower abdomen
	Challenges encountered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving with the baby each time you are traveling
What do you normally do for your health when you are breastfeeding	Health tips when breastfeeding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I visit a health worker immediately whenever you are encounter any medical challenge. • balanced diet
Importance of breastfeeding	Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protects baby from falling sick • well and healthy • develop a bond between the mother and the child.
	why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • But if he does not, he/she gets deformed/malnourished. • Avoid malnutrition • The mother should immediately start breastfeeding as soon as the baby is brought back to her after delivery.
Thought about the use of medication during breastfeeding	views	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You become scared for the child thinking he/she will spread the virus to the baby • It helps you treat the illness

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baby acquires prophylaxis from medicines taken by the mother.
experiences of breastfeeding while on medication	Experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have not encountered any challenge for as long as you swallow the medication on time, you don't experience any challenge. • ART adherence was a challenge to me at the beginning. • I could forget it sometimes and it could bring me weird dreams. • None disclosure to the housemates, hide the drugs such that they do not see it. • I have had issues with breastmilk insufficiency because of being sick and lack of appetite
suggest to a friend who needs to take medications during breastfeeding	Recommends	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would have encouraged her to be well-adherent to her ART to keep her child healthy. • take that medication well since some sicknesses may be transferred to the baby from the mother like flu, and cough. • I would encourage them to swallow the medication if they are sick to protect the health of the baby and hers as well.
How do you find out the safety of medication taken during breastfeeding	Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • health care providers • the internet • hospital • Friends
	why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For some drugs, you may run out of breast milk

Risks involved in self-medication during breastfeeding	Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You might take an overdose The baby may be affected by getting side effects might buy medication that is not supposed to be used when breastfeeding and get side effects
Improve medication use among breastfeeding women	Suggestions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get a prescription from a healthcare provider Clinicians should take the initiative to ask the mother if they are BF or not
Motivation from health workers to breastfeeding mothers while they take medication to ensure that they adhere well	Motivation to adherence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide information through health talks, advertisements emphasizing the importance of taking medication especially when you are sick and breastfeeding
Disclosure of any medications to your partner	Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For emergency support if take medication that is contraindicated to the illness you have or the situation and you get side effects
	Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> but if you haven't disclosed it and he get the medication, it can be difficult for you to explain it to him if he reacts negatively you develop fear that fear Blame from the partner wondering where you contracted the virus stress and pressure on yourself affects adherence lack of support for side effects.
	Motivators for disclosure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The reaction gives you courage I want peace in the relationship For his support if I fail to work trustworthiness without any secrets
	Experiences of disclosure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The doctor disclosed the results to both of us I feared a lot but he encouraged me and advised me to swallow the

		medication even when we both tested HIV positive
	Persons disclosed to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mother
	Reason for choosing the person disclosed to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is because she is my friend, I trust her and she is confidential.
	Challenges of medicine non-disclosure in the community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of confidentiality from persons in the community
	Impact of non-disclosure	Adherence can be affected
	Ways to support disclosure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invited both partners to the health centers and explained to them together for proper details. • find the most convenient time with the spouse for disclosure • educated about the importance of sharing information about the medication they are taking.
experience in study participation	experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquire new knowledge. • I did not get any side effects but I was able to get more information about the disease • I also understood that it is important to participate in these studies because you become informed and are able to support others who are not able to participate.
	Challenges faced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No challenges were faced. • they used to give injections yet I sometimes fear them.

	Thought about breastfeeding women's participation in studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women learn to care for their children learning a lot that you do not know • Healthcare providers are able to learn whether the medication works well among pregnant and breastfeeding women
	Support for BF to participate in research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • educate you about the medication and its side effect • Voluntary consent
Partner consent	experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you do not get approval from him • you have to leave with consent/approval then you go in peace
	Why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • he has a right to refuse you from participating • you may get abused by him
herbs and complementary medicines during breastfeeding	Experiences and advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have used mushrooms to treat colic • The baby did not encounter any side effects. • Pharmaceutical medicines because it's the medicine I use most of the time. • I used Kamunye and Etwatwa, to help wash in the stomach and reduce the pain. I did not get any side effects when using them
	Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • they give you that medication to cure a certain illness and it does not work • difficult to know the right herbal medication and dosage for it.
	preference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmaceutical medicines because it's the medicine I use most of the time. • I think the herbal medication on some level is it good and on another it is bad. • western medication

	Why	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• because western medication• it has been tested before and they provide you with the possible side effects and benefits
	Advise	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• visit a health worker• I would not recommend

CODING FRAMEWORK FOR KII-HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS.

THEME	SUBTHEME	CODES
Messages to women regarding breastfeeding whilst taking medications	Information on safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drugs may cross into BM • Safety of medicine during BF • Medicine may protect the baby • Don't encourage them to take any drugs depending on the condition they're having or the problem they're having. • Always consult a doctor • Weigh the benefit against the risk • Avoid self-prescriptions • Adhere to drugs well • Counsel mother that has fears about safety of drugs during breastfeeding • Not every medicine is safe while breastfeeding • Inform them about possible side effects • Watch out for any side effects
challenges faced in prescribing drugs to BF women	challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No challenge faced • lack of information on the drugs which are excreted • lack of information sources. • BFW don't want to adhere to drugs • You convince them more that the drug will not affect the baby • The dose could be reduced for some drugs • Anxiety, mothers ask many questions to fear of drugs affecting the baby • Some women resist taking drugs because they have alternatives; herbal medicines. • You need to be sure drugs are necessary to give

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have to be conscious about possible side effects to baby and breastmilk • Information on safety is not readily available
Drugs are not recommended during BF	Types of drugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluconazole • Azithromycin • I am not sure • contain caffeine, then codeine • drugs that contain salicylic acids • aspirin • Diazepam • Penicillin • NSAIDS • Anticovulsants • I am not sure • That is difficult, I cant tell now • Tetracyline • Bromoquitrin • mophine
	Why the drugs not recommended	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Side effects to the baby since they are excreted in BM high quantities • Passes through BM and to the baby • Reduce breast Milk supply • Dries breastmilk
Availability of information		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about breastfeeding and medicines is not readily available • Available 60%, we focus more on pregnant women
Adherence to medicines during BF	Challenges.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adherence may be challenging because Women forget to take medicines • Taking the drugs on time is a problem. • They will take the drugs since they may want to protect the baby • Thet have alternatives to take herbal products that may interfere with adherence • They may interrupt treatment if they notice a milk supply • May fear to take drugs because breastmilk may reduce

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear that drugs may affect the baby thus affecting adherence • if higher doses are taken baby may experience side effects • fear of milk disappearance • myths from friends that could affect adherence
	Easiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persons on ART can easily adhere due to fear of infecting the baby • They will take if they are severely sick
Strategies used to minimize infant exposure to medication	strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am not sure • No right strategy mentioned • Give alternative drug • Hold breastfeeding if necessary • I have just heard about the strategies; I dint know any • Express breastmilk before taking drug
Ask if women are breastfeeding before prescribing	Yes/ No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes: not every drug is safe during breastfeeding • Ask how old is the infant
Support to breastfeeding women taking medications	Individual support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reassuring the mother that the medicine is safe for use • Encourage them to disclose drugs to their partners • Advise them to set reminders to take drugs • Listening and responding to their questions • Health education talks • Reminders using phone calls to take medicines • Use peer mothers to support them • Support in nutrition • Give all necessary information about the drug • Discourage them from mixing alcohol and drugs
	Institutional support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research drugs, and deliver the safety information • Counsel them on adherence

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health education of drugs • Encourage them to form support groups
How to ensure that you are providing a safe medication to a breastfeeding woman	Steps taken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consulting and referring for guidance • Find out the drug interactions • Check the drug side effects • Check for drug-drug interactions • Check the MOH guidelines • Read the drug information leaflet • Read literature of the drug
	Why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's a vulnerable group
Recommendations for taking medications with no safety data during breastfeeding	Steps taken	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That is tricky, or I don't know • Read about the side effects • Consider the benefit to risk ration • check with their doctors • Avoid self-prescriptions • Consult a healthcare provider • I would not stop her completely to take the drug • Give alternative drug • Check out for any upcoming side effects • Call them to stop the drug • To pump • Stop breastfeeding
Sources that you use to acquire information on medication use during BF	Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet • Medscape • Uganda Clinical guidelines • Other online sources • Consult Colleagues • BNF • Research forums • Websites: NDA •
	Reasons for checking information sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty about the safety of the drugs. • To find out if the drug is recommended • Information is readily available

<p>Ways to improve healthcare services for breastfeeding women taking medicines in your department/facility</p>	<p>suggestions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't know • healthy talks. • education sessions on nutrition • conducive environment • provide enough information • Buy drugs for breastfeeding women to improve adherence • Incentives may not be a guarantee for them to take medicines well
<p>Thoughts about the inclusion of Breastfeeding women in studies investigating drugs</p>	<p>Reasons</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To find out about the safety of the drug • I wouldn't advise them to be included in the study • Yes, but consider the safety of the baby • Include them to acquire safety data on that population • Give them necessary information about the study risks and benefits
	<p>Why</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Because it's a vulnerable group • No less evidence about the drugs thus fear of causing unknown side effects • They are minority group • Get safety evidence in the breastfeeding population • To get women perspectives about study participation • Women acquire more information on their health
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • some women shy away from study participation • encourage women to participate
	<p>Factors to consider.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety of the baby and the mother. • Ability to closely monitor the mother and the baby. • Risk to benefit ration
<p>Enablers for breastfeeding women to participate in studies</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribute to their well-being by providing milk, and porridge to increase breastmilk and boost their nutrition status: nutritional support

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give them priority and reduce waiting hours in the facility. • Study procedures should not take long and they should be few. • Secure a comfortable space for breastfeeding and babies to play • adequate follow-up • Nutritional support • Continuous health education talks • Maintain ethics; confidentiality • Friendly environment • Give them all information about the study • Incentives • Incentives but they may see it as coercion to participate • Support from Recs bodies • Community sensitization • Transport refund
<p>challenges faced by breastfeeding women taking medicines</p>	<p>Facility-based challenges.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • long journey to the facility to go and get that medicine.
	<p>Individual-based challenges.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of money for good nutrition. • Lack of transport money to the facility. • Poor nutrition leading to low breastmilk for infant • Lack of money to buy prescribed medicines • Inadequate information on nutrition • May forget to take their drugs • May have poor adhere since they handle baby too, thus forget to take drugs • Mothers on contraception report breastmilk reduction: injectable, implants • Stigma that could lead to poor adherence • Reduced milk supply after taking some drugs • Lack of support from partners

Herbal intake during breastfeeding	Advise/observations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I wouldn't advise any mother to take herbs during breastfeeding • it is ok if taken in the right quantity • do not take • mothers have more hope in herbal products
	reasons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross over breast milk to the baby, and maybe harm the baby • May not have approved dose • Unknown concentrations • No measurement taken like dose and temperature to determine the dose • Herbal drug may not have enough safety evidence
	Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The dosage is unknown. • May cause side effects to the infant • May cause side effects to baby and mother • Drug drug interactions-western medicines and herbal
Advice to breastfeeding women who consume drugs and herbal or natural products co currently	Advise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advise to stop and take prescribed drugs • not mix a lot of drugs because these are poisons. • Avoid mixing western drugs and herbal products • To stop because herbs may cause unknown side effects
Support to BF taking herbal drugs.	Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Education • Serve them quickly to avoid the frustration that takes them to herbal stores where they are served quickly • Conduct research • to take them in intervals ie one to two hours apart. • Community sensitization • Regulate the herbalists • Filter the herbal adverts

CODING FRAMEWORK FOR NDA PERSONNEL.

THEME	SUBTHEME	CODES
Thoughts about the inclusion of breastfeeding (BF) women in studies investigating drugs?	Agree, and why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • find out how safe the drugs • risk to benefit balance • Put measures to avoid harm • Address the knowledge gap in the population • Take safety precautions during study • No serious effects have occurred affected breastfeeding • To provide new evidence in different populations • Uncertainty about the drug
	Disagree and why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's a necessary evil: we cant expose baby to unknown drug • due to the risk of infant exposure, it's better not to include them • Exposure of baby to drug with unknown safety evidence
Challenges faced in reviewing protocols for breastfeeding and pregnant women	barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited experts or • no experienced healthcare personnel in review protocol in that population • Insufficient information makes review difficult • lack of evidence since most clinical trials exclude women • lack of safety data • Insufficient information on drugs on investigator brochure and product leaflet

Barriers faced in prescribing drugs to BF women		
Support to breastfeeding women taking medications	Individual support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> women's education about research provide necessary information during the consenting process encourage them to report medicine AEs Do pharmacovigilance Conduct pharmacokinetic studies Monitor women on investigational drugs
	Institutional support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> detailed research for safety evidence pharmacovigilance providing safe medicines. -look out for safety profiles and communicate -monitor and manage AES. -communication; healthcare providers, regulatory authorities, and patients
ways to provide safe medication to breastfeeding women.	Facilitator to safety medication among BF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> education on self-medication encourage the use of prescriptions healthcare providers should receive continuous medical education on drugs Prescribe drugs that are safe in BF Risk to benefit ratio Healthcare workers should be informed about drugs prescribed in breastfeeding CMEs for healthcare workers Health workers should give proper medicine instructions Women should follow medicine instructions Design the protocol well

Knowledge of drugs not recommended during breastfeeding		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentioned drugs and reasons • Did not know the drugs
Recommendations given to women taking medications with no safety data during breastfeeding	Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • follow the health worker's advice • follow drug instructions • Take medicines as prescribed by the doctor • Avoid self-prescriptions and self-medication • Report any AE experienced by the baby • report to NDA via platforms; toll free line, whatup • Inform healthcare providers that they are breastfeeding • Ask for medicines instructions and ensure they understand the instructions • Timing of breastfeeding in relation to taking medicines • Avoid taking medicines unless its necessary • Pump and dump breastmilk • Avoid hormonal contraceptive that may affect breastfeeding
Drugs are not recommended during BF	Types of drugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tetracycline • ciprofloxacin • Opioid • Chlorophenol • Anti galactoglobin • cant think of any right now • Is this a test • Chemotherapy • I don't know • I have seen any drug contraindicated in breastfeeding
	Why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • because of their effects on the bone growth of the baby
Sources that provide information on medication use during BF	sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the patient information leaflet • Product summary characteristic • PubMed,google • Patient feedback

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • product of analysis for safety information • BNF websites • Investigator brochure • UCG • HIV guidelines • Drug vendors or salesmen • Health workers in village clinic may not know the sources
<p>Strategies used to minimize infant exposure to medication</p>	<p>strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • monitor drug intake and breastfeeding time. • If not certain, the baby may not breastfeed • alternative routes of administration or exposure; cream • I don't know or not sure • Consider PK/PD • Risk to benefit ratio of breastfeeding or stop BF while on medication • Rational drug use • Manufacture drugs that don't cross the mammary glands
<p>How to improve healthcare services for pregnant and breastfeeding women in research?</p>	<p>individual</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutritional support; supplements • Proper documentation and reporting of SAEs • inclusion of BF women in research • safety mechanisms to reduce infant exposure to drugs • manage and monitoring AES • encourage communication by regulatory authorities, healthcare providers and patients • provide prophylaxis to infants to reduce spread of diseases • recommendation on SAE, Improve documentation of SAEs • provide a friendly space or room to get healthcare • free consultation • health education of dangers of alcohol intake

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screen for breastmilk to check if its fit for infant • researchers should find out the perspectives of women regarding breastfeeding and medicines
	facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • active follow up • Proper documentation of SAEs
Enablers of breastfeeding/pregnant women to participate in studies	Enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inform BF about the risk-to-benefit ratio • compensation for any injury • Proper management if enrolled and monitoring for AEs • Give information on study participation • Give credible and transparent information about the study

CODING FRAMEWORK FOR PARTNERS OF BREASTFEEDING WOMEN.

THEME	SUBTHEME	CODES
Practices during breastfeeding	Practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They take porridge for breast milk secretion. • I usually see her using millet or soya to get breast milk. While breastfeeding they don't want the breastmilk to drop/pour on the baby. • They don't allow breastmilk to drop on the baby • Maintain a balanced diet to acquire breastmilk • Take a nutritious diet
Partner support for breastfeeding women	support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support • Probably if the woman is not yours. But if the woman is yours, why not support her. That is impossible. • Nutritional support • Advise women to go to health facility • Support her to maintain hygiene for both mother and baby • Treatment buddies to remind them take medicines • Encourage her to adhere to medicines • Motivation to take medicines while breastfeeding • counselling
Barriers to partner support towards women taking drugs and breastfeeding	Barriers to partner support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women demand more support than the partner's financial ability • Women are unhygienic, men separate beds or run away from home • Lack of funds to support with family needs • When the relationship is unstable • Financial challenges
Enablers for partner Support to breastfeeding women	Facilitator to medicine intake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support • Reminders to take medicines. • Reminders to take meals on time

while taking medicines		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivation and encouragement
Disclosure of medicines	Experiences/ Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • financial support to attend the hospital visits • Psychological support from partner • Take woman to hospital for the healthcare to aid disclosure • It can lead to domestic violence if not conducted well • People don't disclose for protective reasons • It is not easy due to fear of the results • Partner cannot support you if unaware of the situation
	challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harshness from the partner's side • Love for the partner • Fear for marriage break up
	Strategies that women use to avoid disclosure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting someone else they trust say at the facility where she gets her medication • Hide medicines with relatives • Under the bed • Extreme corners • handbags
Barriers to non-disclosure		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Men are harsh and could domestically abuse the women • Fear of the outcome
Enablers of disclosure	Facilitators of disclosure of medicines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go to the Health Facility and talk to a health worker for supportive disclosure. • If the couple has a good relationship with each other • Your partner should be your friend • Good explanation from the partner explaining the situation and the partner should listen
Disadvantages of non-disclosure		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affects adherence to drugs

Breastfeeding women's participation in studies	experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spread the disease to baby • It is good, that women acquire knowledge. • The bad I see in it mostly, is that a breastfeeding mother may come in those studies and pick bad habits /ideas from fellow breastfeeding mothers. • It's not necessary for one to refuse a woman to participate in a study • I cannot refuse her from participating in a study. • Acquire knowledge about the baby • Not necessary to refuse women to participate • Women acquire new knowledge • Get knowledge for mother and baby
men influence their partners in decision-making to participate in clinical	Influence	Encourage people in the community to participate to add to new research knowledge
	Importance of women's participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquire more knowledge on breastfeeding • Acquire knowledge on studies • Depends on the relation; some could refuse participation • Trustworthy in the relationship • Provide financial support for transport • Men decide as the head of the family, if he disagrees, then the woman can't participate • Men way the benefit against the risk to make a decision
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on study participation
Partner consent		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have to give her permission to participate, I have to know what procedures will be conducted on the woman • Spouse has to inform the partner about participation • I sign the partner consent form after checking the details of the study • Suspicious about the studies

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Woman cannot travel without the spouse approval
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